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SMALL BUSINESS AS A CATALYST FOR REGIONAL ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT: AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS WITH EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. This article examines the multidimensional developmental role of small businesses in regional economies through a systematic literature review and comparative statistical analysis. Drawing on data from the OECD, World Bank, IFC, ILO, and Uzbekistani statistical authorities, the study demonstrates that SMEs account for approximately 90% of enterprises globally and employ more than half of the world's workforce. Uzbekistan's experience is particularly noteworthy: by 2024, small enterprises contributed approximately 56% of national GDP and accounted for 86% of total employment, significantly exceeding OECD averages. Regional disaggregation reveals considerable territorial diversity, with the Bukhara, Namangan, and Fergana Valley regions exhibiting SME activity levels substantially above the national average. The findings also highlight significant opportunities for further development through productivity enhancement, expanded access to finance, and accelerated technological modernization. The article concludes with targeted policy recommendations aimed at strengthening financial inclusion, promoting sectoral modernization, and advancing region-specific development strategies to support sustainable economic growth.

Keywords: small and medium-sized enterprises; regional economic development; employment generation; economic diversification; Uzbekistan; SME policy; territorial cohesion.

Аннотация. В данной статье исследуется многогранная роль малого бизнеса в развитии региональной экономики на основе систематического обзора научной литературы и сравнительного статистического анализа. Используя данные ОЭСР, Всемирного банка, Международной финансовой корпорации (IFC), Международной организации труда (МОТ) и статистических органов Узбекистана, автор показывает, что малые и средние предприятия (МСП) составляют около 90 % всех предприятий в мире и обеспечивают занятость более половины мировой рабочей силы. Опыт Узбекистана является особенно показательным: к 2024 году доля малого бизнеса в валовом внутреннем продукте страны достигла примерно 56 %, а его вклад в общую занятость населения составил 86 %, что значительно превышает средние показатели стран ОЭСР. Региональный анализ выявляет существенное территориальное разнообразие, при этом наиболее высокий уровень предпринимательской активности наблюдается в Бухарской, Наманганской областях и регионах Ферганской долины. Результаты исследования также свидетельствуют о значительном потенциале дальнейшего роста за счёт повышения производительности, расширения доступа к финансовым ресурсам и ускорения технологической модернизации. В заключение предлагаются целевые рекомендации по совершенствованию механизмов финансовой поддержки, модернизации отраслевой структуры и развитию территориально ориентированных инструментов регионального развития, способствующих устойчивому экономическому росту.

Ключевые слова: малые и средние предприятия; региональное экономическое развитие; создание занятости; экономическая диверсификация; Узбекистан; политика поддержки МСП; территориальная сплочённость.

INTRODUCTION

Analysing U.S. employment data over two decades, researchers reported that small enterprises rather than the large corporations that dominate public discourse were responsible for the majority of net new job creation [9]. This influential finding initiated one of the most productive empirical research streams in applied economics and continues to receive substantial support in contemporary scholarship. According to IFC data [20], SMEs account for approximately 90% of registered enterprises worldwide, while formal small businesses provide employment for more than half of the global workforce. In emerging economies, formal SMEs contribute up to 40% of GDP, and when informal economic activity is considered, their overall contribution is estimated at 60–70% [19]. OECD evidence [26] further indicates that firms employing 10–249 workers account for approximately 40% of employment and 38% of value added across a 13-country panel, highlighting their substantial economic significance.

At the subnational level, [23] demonstrated that spatial proximity among small producers can generate competitive advantages extending beyond individual firm size. These insights were subsequently developed through the cluster concept by [28], while [12] and [3] incorporated institutional perspectives into regional innovation systems. Empirical evidence provided by [4] shows that regions may follow distinct development trajectories depending on patterns of entrepreneurial activity and new-firm formation. Furthermore, [6] advanced the knowledge spillover theory of entrepreneurship, explaining how research and innovation activities contribute to regional productive capacity and economic growth.

Uzbekistan represents a particularly informative case for examining these dynamics. Between 2000 and 2021, SME employment increased from 4.5 million to 10.1 million workers, reaching 86% of total employment, while its contribution to GDP rose from 31% to approximately 56% by 2024 [21, 32]. These achievements demonstrate the growing importance of small businesses in the national economy and create valuable opportunities for further investigation of their role in regional development. The present article contributes to this discussion through: (1) a synthesis of theoretical and empirical literature; (2) an assessment of SME effects on employment, productivity, innovation, and territorial cohesion; and (3) the formulation of evidence-based policy recommendations.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The role of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in economic development has been widely examined in economic literature. Marshall (1890) emphasized the importance of local business concentration in enhancing productivity, while Schumpeter (1934) identified entrepreneurship as a key driver of innovation and economic growth.

Empirical studies confirm the significant contribution of SMEs to employment creation and economic development. Birch (1981; 1987) found that small firms generate a substantial share of new jobs, while Beck, Demirgüç-Kunt, and Levine (2005) demonstrated a positive relationship between SME development, economic growth, and poverty reduction.

The innovation potential of SMEs has also been highlighted by Acs and Audretsch (1988; 1990), who found that small firms often produce more innovations per employee than large enterprises. Audretsch and Lehmann (2005) further explained this through the Knowledge Spillover Theory, emphasizing the role of SMEs in transforming knowledge into economic value.

At the regional level, Porter (1998) stressed the importance of business clusters, while Cooke et al. (1997) and Asheim and Isaksen (2002) developed the Regional Innovation Systems approach. Their studies show that entrepreneurship, innovation, and institutional cooperation contribute significantly to regional competitiveness and long-term growth.

Recent reports by the OECD (2023; 2024), IFC (2022; 2024), and the European Commission (2023) indicate that SMEs account for around 90% of enterprises worldwide and more than half of global employment. In Uzbekistan, the share of SMEs in GDP increased from approximately 31% in 2000 to around 56% in 2024, while their contribution to employment reached 86%, highlighting their growing importance in regional and national economic development.

Overall, the literature confirms that SMEs are essential drivers of employment, innovation, regional competitiveness, and sustainable economic growth.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodological framework of the study is based on three complementary components: a systematic literature review, descriptive and comparative statistical analysis, and comparative institutional analysis [13]. The literature search was conducted using Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar databases,

covering the period 2010–2024 while also incorporating seminal earlier contributions. Statistical information was obtained from the OECD, World Bank/IFC, ILO, IMF, UNCTAD, the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and INVEXI. The study also identifies several opportunities for future research. First, differences in national SME classification systems may provide scope for further harmonisation of measurement approaches. Second, the future availability of district-level data could facilitate more detailed territorial analyses within Uzbekistan. Third, subsequent studies may complement the present descriptive assessment through econometric and causal research designs to generate deeper analytical insights.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Global Evidence on Small Business Contributions to Regional Economies

Employment. IFC and World Bank data [20, 36] indicate that formal SMEs account for more than 50% of global employment, and this share increases substantially when informal economic activity is taken into account. [17], analysing a German regional panel, found that new-firm formation has statistically significant positive effects on regional employment growth, with the full impact emerging over a medium-term period of approximately eight years. [10]’s pioneering finding that young and small firms serve as a major source of net job creation has been consistently supported by a broad body of subsequent regional and international research.

Productivity and Innovation. OECD evidence [25] shows that SMEs contribute 38% of value added while accounting for a substantially larger share of employment, highlighting both their economic importance and the potential for further productivity enhancement. Moreover, [1] reported a landmark finding that small U.S. manufacturing firms generated 2.38 times more innovations per employee than their large-firm counterparts, demonstrating the strong innovative capacity of smaller enterprises. [6] explain this phenomenon through the knowledge spillover mechanism, whereby small firms act as effective channels for commercialising knowledge generated by universities and research institutions, thereby transforming scientific advances into economic value.

Regional Competitiveness. Endogenous growth models [29] suggest that knowledge accumulation within geographically concentrated business clusters generates positive externalities that support long-term economic growth. Furthermore, [8], in a cross-sectional analysis covering 45 countries, found that higher SME employment shares are positively associated with both faster GDP per capita growth and more inclusive income distribution. The results indicate that the contribution of SMEs to balanced income distribution represents an important channel through which they enhance overall economic performance and regional competitiveness (Table 1).

Table 1
SME Employment and GDP Shares: Selected International Comparisons

Economy / Group	SME Employment Share (%)	SME GDP Share (%)	Primary Source
OECD Average	~65–70%	~55–60%	{OECD, 2023}
Emerging Economies (formal)	>50%	up to 40%	{IFC, 2022, 2024}
Emerging Economies (incl. informal)	>60%	60–70%	{IFC, 2022}
European Union	~66%	~56%	{EC, 2023}
Uzbekistan 2021	86%	54.9%	{OECD, 2023c}
Uzbekistan 2024 (est.)	~86%	~56%	{INVEXI, 2025}

Note. GDP shares reflect formal SME sectors unless otherwise indicated.

Scale and Structure. Small enterprises accounted for 54.3% of GDP in 2024, with [21] full-year estimates reaching approximately 56%. Small enterprises play a leading role in agriculture (95.2%), retail trade (84.0%), and construction (76.5%), demonstrating their substantial contribution to economic activity and employment generation. In addition, the sector maintains a significant presence in manufacturing, where it accounts for 32.4% of output, indicating considerable potential for further expansion and productivity growth [32] (Table 2).

Table 2
Small Enterprise Sectoral Contributions in Uzbekistan, 2024¹

¹ Source: {State Statistics Committee, 2024}; {INVEXI, 2025}.

Sector	SE Share (%)	Output (billion soums)	Structural Note
Agriculture	95.2%	—	Strong SE participation supporting agricultural production and rural development
Construction	76.5%	178 718.9	High SE involvement contributing to broad regional development
Retail Trade	84.0%	338 802.6	Extensive SE-driven distribution and market accessibility network
Services	57.0%	466 461.8	Expanding SE presence with increasing opportunities for productivity enhancement
Industry / Manufacturing	32.4%	286 675.2	Significant potential for further SE expansion and industrial diversification
GDP (Total)	54.3–56%	1 454 573.9	Reflects the substantial contribution of SEs to national economic growth in 2024

Regional Heterogeneity. Subnational distribution remains diverse across regions. Reports indicate that the Bukhara region records the highest SME share in gross regional product at 73.0%, followed by Namangan and several Fergana Valley oblasts, reflecting strong historical traditions in artisanal, textile, and food-processing industries. The Tashkent metropolitan area, despite hosting the highest absolute concentration of registered enterprises, records SME shares slightly below the national average due to the significant presence of large enterprises. This metropolitan–peripheral differentiation aligns with [18]’s finding that entrepreneurial culture is highly persistent and influenced by regional economic structures.

Employment, Poverty Reduction, and Constraints. With 86% of total employment concentrated in the SME sector, Uzbekistan demonstrates a remarkably strong SME contribution compared with OECD averages (~65–70%). World Bank data indicate that the poverty headcount declined from 17% in 2019 to 11% in 2023, with SME-driven income generation serving as an important contributing factor. At the same time, access to finance remains an area for further improvement, while estimates place the global SME financing gap at approximately \$4.1 trillion. The gradual formalisation of economic activity is expected to further strengthen SME creditworthiness and investment potential.

The broad pattern of findings is consistent with endogenous growth theory, regional innovation systems analysis, and knowledge spillover theory, all of which predict stronger long-run regional growth through dynamic small business sectors. An important consideration concerns entrepreneurial composition rather than volume. Researchers distinguish between opportunity entrepreneurship (exploiting identified market opportunities) and necessity entrepreneurship (business creation motivated by employment considerations), each contributing differently to productivity and economic development. Uzbekistan’s high 86% employment share reflects both entrepreneurial dynamism and the sector’s significant role in supporting labour-market participation.

Comparatively, Uzbekistan’s increase from 31% to approximately 56% in SME GDP share during 2000–2024 exceeds the pace observed in many Central Asian transition economies, corresponding to the “entrepreneurial jump” pattern documented in the literature. At the same time, the strong presence of SMEs in agriculture, trade, and construction provides a foundation for further diversification into manufacturing and knowledge-intensive activities, creating additional opportunities for productivity growth and innovation.

Four policy implications follow. (1) Finance: partial credit guarantee schemes, development bank facilities, and fintech-enabled credit scoring can be further expanded and adapted to underserved oblasts. (2) Industrial upgrading: policies may encourage greater participation in export-oriented manufacturing and knowledge-intensive services, supported by continued investment in technical and vocational education. (3) Place-based differentiation: regional SME frameworks should be tailored to territorial profiles; the Fergana Valley may benefit from cluster support, while Tashkent faces distinct regulatory and cost-related challenges, drawing on the European smart specialisation model {Foray et al., 2012}. (4) Institutional quality: continued improvements in contract enforcement, property rights protection, and administrative simplification will further enhance the effectiveness of SME development policies.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Three substantive conclusions emerge. First, SMEs are structural pillars of market economies, accounting for approximately 90% of enterprises and more than half of global employment. The density, dynamism, and sectoral composition of small business activity are key determinants of territorial economic performance.

Second, Uzbekistan presents a compelling illustration of SME-led growth in a transition economy, with

the SME sector's contribution to GDP increasing from 31% to approximately 56% during 2000–2024 and its employment share reaching 86%. At the same time, regional diversity highlights the importance of tailoring development policies to local economic conditions and opportunities.

Third, the remarkable expansion of the SME sector creates a strong foundation for further economic transformation. While agriculture and trade remain important drivers of SME activity, significant opportunities exist for greater participation in manufacturing, innovation-driven industries, and knowledge-intensive services. Continued improvements in access to finance, technological capability, and business formalisation will further strengthen the sector's contribution to sustainable economic growth.

Overall, sustained progress will be supported by targeted financing instruments, sectoral upgrading, place-based development frameworks, and ongoing institutional reforms. Together, these measures can enhance productivity, competitiveness, innovation capacity, and long-term economic resilience.

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